

Cite as: Parappully, Jose. (2007). Effects of Sexual Abuse: Data from Clinical Experience (Version 1.0). Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies, Jan-June 2007 (10/1), 155-174. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4266872>

Effects of Sexual Abuse Data from Clinical Experience

Jose Parappully SDB1

Bosco Psychological Services, New Delhi

Abstract: A survey of Catholic psychologists and counsellors in India shows that many psychotherapy clients report experience of sexual abuse. This article describes the effects of sexual abuse as reported by and seen in these psychotherapy clients. Data show that sexual abuse profoundly affects the survivors physically, psychologically and spiritually. Knowledge of these effects is useful for sexual abuse survivors in general and for their formators and spiritual directors.

Keywords: Self-concept, sexual abuse, physical consequences, psychological consequences, spiritual consequences.

An earlier article in this Journal (Parappully, 2003) presented data from a research study on sexual abuse. The focus of that article was the prevalence rate of sexual abuse among psychotherapy clients. This current article describes the effects of sexual abuse reported and manifested by the same clients. An earlier article in this Journal (Parappully, 2003) presented data from a research study on sexual abuse. The focus of that article was the prevalence rate of sexual abuse among psychotherapy clients. This current article describes the effects of sexual abuse reported and manifested by the same clients.

One hundred and fifty five Catholic psychologists and counsellors were mailed a three-page questionnaire (Parappully, 2003). In one section of the questionnaire, respondents were asked to briefly describe the effects of abuse they noticed in their sexually abused clients in four areas: physical, mental, emotional and spiritual. Of the 60 (38.7%) questionnaires that were returned, 13 could not be in-

cluded in the study for a variety of reasons. Of the remaining 47 questionnaires included in the study, 25 were from female respondents and 22 from male respondents. The total number of clients about whom data were provided by these 47 clinicians was 17,522. Of these clients 12,304 (70.22%) were women and 5218 (29.78%) men. One hundred and fifty five Catholic psychologists and counsellors were mailed a three-page questionnaire (Parappully, 2003). In one section of the questionnaire, respondents were asked to briefly describe the effects of abuse they noticed in their sexually abused clients in four areas: physical, mental, emotional and spiritual. Of the 60 (38.7%) questionnaires that were returned, 13 could not be included in the study for a variety of reasons. Of the remaining 47 questionnaires included in the study, 25 were from female respondents and 22 from male respondents. The total number of clients about whom data were provided by these 47 clinicians was 17,522. Of these clients 12,304 (70.22%) were women and 5218 (29.78%) men.

Content analysis of the descriptions of effects of sexual abuse in the 47 questionnaires was done from a phenomenological perspective (Giorgi, 1970, 1985) following techniques suggested by Miles and Huberman (1994). Lists of effects in the four areas were created by writing out every effect mentioned. There were a total of 617 references in the four areas (physical = 112, mental = 226, emotional = 145 and spiritual 134) across respondents. References to similar effects in each area were then clustered together and labelled. These clusters were further integrated under more inclusive labels. As several similar effects were listed under mental as well as emotional, these were amalgamated during analysis into one new category – Psychological (including mental and emotional). Hence the effects reported are described below under three categories — physical, psychological and spiritual. All the effects enumerated by the respondents are listed below. It is important to note that not all the survivors of abuse are affected in the same way or have the same consequences. The numbers in brackets indicate the total number of times each of the effects were mentioned by the respondents. Content analysis of the descriptions of effects of sexual abuse in the 47 questionnaires was done from a phenomenological perspective

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Physical Consequences (112)

Appearance (27)

Survivors often present a sad, depressed or forlorn look (11). Their energy level is often low (7). They appear rigid and their ways of posturing and way of walking is affected (5). Some of them do not care for grooming and are untidy in their appearance especially in dress (2). Loss or gain of weight happens (1). Their physical growth is affected (1).

Sexual Behaviour (30)

Survivors experience hyperarousal and are often preoccupied with sex (5). They show hypersensitivity to touch (5). Need to masturbate becomes quite compelling (8). They go on to abuse others (3). They engage in sexual activities promiscuously (3). They encourage others into sexual activity (2). They get infected by sexually transmitted diseases (2). Women experience menstrual disorders and other gynaecological problems (2).

Psychosomatic Reactions (21)

Survivors experience psychosomatic reactions such as headaches, heaviness in the head, back pain, colds, allergies, and rashes (15).

Sleep is disturbed (3). Tremor of hands and fingers (1), excessive sweating of palms (1) and hyperventilation (1) are some other effects.

General Behaviour (14)

Survivors are rigid and controlled in their behaviour (1). They are physically withdrawn (2). They are not able to face people (1). They find it difficult to speak loud if they had been told to keep quiet during the abuse (1). They manifest a hysterical and histrionic style (1). They engage in aggressive or passive-aggressive behaviour (2). They engage in compulsive washing (1). They run away from home (1). In facing situations or persons presenting themselves or imagined as potentially abusive or at the prospect of abuse coming to light, they experience panic attacks (1). Men develop feminine mannerisms (1). When abuse results in pregnancy women have recourse to abortion (2).

Body Concept and Care (11)

Survivors neglect care of their body (3). They feel their body is unclean or dirty (2). They have a negative attitude toward their body and body processes (2). They have hatred toward their body (1). They have a preoccupation with being obsessively clean (1). They have uneasy experiences in the body (1). They are unable to experience pleasure (1).

Addictive Behaviour (9)

In trying to numb their feelings, they have recourse to alcohol or drugs (5). They suffer from anorexia, bulimia and other eating disorders (3). They engage in hedonistic or pleasure-seeking behaviours (1).

Psychological Consequences (371)

Relationships (74)

Sexual abuse affects relationships negatively: in general (7), and particularly with those of the opposite sex (2). Survivors experience inability to relate deeply with others (10). They even avoid friendships with those of the same sex (1). Their ability to trust gets seriously impaired: the adult world in general (15), themselves (1), and

the opposite sex (1), particularly men (5). They experience aversion and hatred toward the abuser (1) and persons of the same sex as the abuser (9). They become overly dependent on others (3), unable to be assertive (2), oversensitive to social disapproval (1), as well as judgmental of others (1). They become timid in social situations (2). They have difficulty in confiding in others (1). They lie (1); manipulate (1); blame (1); and find fault with others (1). They try to protect the perpetrator and save his/her family from dishonour (1). They are unable to create new meaningful relations (4). They experience a craving for love and affection (3).

Self Concept (72)

Survivors of sexual abuse experience poor self-esteem (24). They are plagued by feelings of inferiority (7), inadequacy (2) and insecurity (2) and rejection (1). They consider themselves “damaged goods” (3). They condemn themselves (2). They feel ashamed (7), dirty (3), used (3); no good (2); unlovable (2); something is wrong with them (2); cheated and taken as a plaything (1). They feel self-conscious (2). They lack trust in themselves (2). They feel lack of freedom to be themselves (2) and the need to “put on a mask.” (1). They feel a great need for recognition and attention (4).

Cognitive Functions (37)

Survivors suffer from poor concentration (12). They express extreme paranoia (6). They lose touch with reality (4). They appear restless and preoccupied (3). They appear blank and disturbed (3). They become very indecisive (2). They lose motivation (2). They are unable to think clearly (1). They develop problems with memory (1). They are extremely defensive to prevent the “bad me” coming into consciousness (1). They are given to excessive fantasy (1). They suffer nervous breakdown (1).

Fear (36)

Survivors live a life of fear (11); fear of men (7); of the perpetrator (3); of the opposite sex (3); of being abused again (2); of one's own sexuality (1); of one's own body (1); of being taken advantage of (1); of being alone (1), of darkness (1); of noise (1); of strangers (1); and of exposure of the abuse (1). Fear finds expression in nightmares (2).

Anger (35)

Survivors become angry persons (24). They are angry at the perpetrator (3) and angry at themselves (1). They become irritable for little things (3). They want to avenge the abuse (3). They express their anger in covert ways (1).

Guilt Feelings (32)

Nature of the guilt was not specified.

Depression (32)

Survivors feel depressed (14). They withdraw from life and tend to isolate themselves (10). They are pessimistic about the future (1). They experience feelings of hurt (2) hopelessness (1) and abandonment (1); and They brood over their abuse experience (1). They carry the burden of keeping the abuse secret (1). They cry easily (1).

Disturbed Sexuality (21)

Sexual abuse survivors experience intense and sometimes uncontrollable craving for sexual intimacy (6). They are afraid of (2) and lack desire to enter marriage (2), and if they marry, find it difficult to settle down in marriage (1). They experience conflict (2) and guilt (2) over sexual desires and impulses. They develop homosexual orientation (2). They experience sexual identity confusion (1). They develop negative attitude toward sexuality and pleasure (1). They are vulnerable to further abuse (1). They are unwilling to talk about sexuality (1).

Anxiety (14)

Survivors experience anxiety: generalized (10); being infected with HIV/AIDS/STD (2); about pregnancy (1); and illness (1).

Suicidal (12)

Feelings in General (3)

Survivors have difficulties with feelings (1). They experience extreme emotions (1). They repress feelings (1).

Addictions (2)

Survivors get addicted to food (1), to drugs and alcohol (1).

Obsessive-Compulsive Behaviours (1)

Spiritual Consequences (134)

Effect on Relationship with God (43)

Sexual victimization negatively affects survivors' relationship with God in different ways. It leads to questioning and even loss of faith in God (5). A question that many survivors ask is "How could God allow this to happen to me?" Another is "Where was God?" Their faith in a loving, caring and provident God is profoundly shaken by their experience of victimization (6). Faith and trust is often replaced by anger toward God who permitted the victimization (3). They feel alienated and even rejected by God (2). Women survivors find it difficult to relate to masculine God (1).

Their strong sense of guilt leads them to doubt God's forgiveness (6). "Will God forgive me?" is a question heard from many survivors. They consider that they have sinned grievously and God will punish them for this (16). Moreover, the image of a punishing God gets fortified in their minds, making closeness to and intimacy with God difficult. Their inability to forgive themselves (4) makes acceptance of God's forgiveness all the more difficult.

Feelings of Guilt and Unworthiness (40)

Survivors are plagued by feelings of guilt (19) and unworthiness (16). Even though they have been victimized, they feel they have somehow contributed to it or brought it upon themselves. The fact that they experienced some pleasure (that naturally accompanies sexual experience) confounds the feeling of guilt. The high value that society and church accord virginity and chastity and which they have internalized makes them feel that they have soiled or lost something very precious and that they cannot be whole again. They experience themselves as sinners (5) and feel a strong need to make reparation. For some survivors becoming a priest or religious is one way of reparation.

Effect on Prayer and Sacramental Life (28)

Sexual victimization affects prayer and sacramental life. Survivors lose taste for and interest in prayer. Some are unable to pray. Day dreaming in prayer is quite frequent. Guilt and feelings of un-

worthiness keep them away from sacraments. Some are ashamed to go to confession and tend to neglect the Eucharist. Piety often becomes just an external show or observance.

Some take refuge and seek solace in prayer and devotional practices. They love to spend time in the chapel and can be seen as very prayerful. However, much of their prayer is self-accusatory and pleading for forgiveness. Many survivors frequent Retreat Houses seeking healing, solace and as way of reparation.

Vocational Disillusionment (7)

Victimization leads to loss of purpose and meaning in their religious vocation. Feelings of guilt, impurity and unworthiness lead to their experiencing the making and/or living of the vow of chastity as a living lie. They feel hypocritical and doubt the genuineness of their vocation. Some decide to leave religious life for this reason. For others commitment to chastity becomes superficial in the sense it is limited to avoidance of further victimization than to growing in genuine love.

Disillusionment with Church Authority and Institution (7)

When the victimizer is an authority figure in the Church the attitude of anger, resentment and inability to forgive the victimizer gets generalized to authority figures and institutions they represent. Survivors get disillusioned with Church and religious institutions and authorities. They experience loss of trust in their religious superiors because survivors believe that they are in connivance with or protect Church personnel. They see celibacy as a hoax and believe that many in the Church lead a hypocritical life.

Perfectionism and Scrupulosity (5)

Guilt and fear of punishment lead to scrupulosity and perfectionism. Survivors live a very controlled and fearful life so as to avoid failure and wrongdoing. On the other hand, the feeling "Everything is lost, so why bother!" leads to an attitude of "Anything is okay!" and consequent indifference and re-victimization.

Other (4)

Survivors experience difficulty in internalizing spiritual values. They have difficulty in community living. They experience loss of

purpose and meaning. They are in permanent mourning, grieving the loss of their virginity.

Discussion and Conclusions

Data from this study show that sexual abuse profoundly affects survivors—physically, psychologically and spiritually. It affects particularly their self-concept, emotions, attitudes, mental functioning, sexuality, relationships and their spirituality. This study confirms that effects found in various studies in the West on effects of sexual abuse (Briere, 1992; Browne & Finkelhor, 2000; Wolfe, 1999) are prevalent among abuse survivors in this country as well. These western studies have consistently found that sexual abuse has a negative impact on self-concept, affect, mental functioning, sexuality and relationships. This study has provided data on the effect on spirituality more in detail than those usually found in those other studies. Sexual abuse affects one's relationship to God, prayer and sacramental life in significantly negative ways.

Data from this study do not highlight some of the post-traumatic stress symptoms such as complex re-experience of the abuse in flashbacks, dysregulation of affect, and dissociation that other studies (Briere, 1996; Kendall-Tackett, Williams, & Finkelhor, 1993) have shown as major effects of sexual abuse. However, the physical consequences found in this study are like those of persons traumatized by mutilation or loss of limb (P. Lourdes, personal communication, April 25, 2005). This shows that survivors have experienced their abuse as a traumatic violation of their bodies, even if classic symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) are not evidenced or reported by subjects in this study.

The results of this study can be a source of knowledge and relief to survivors of sexual abuse. They can recognize that the experiences they have are not unique to them but are common consequences of sexual abuse. Sometimes survivors are bewildered by their experiences and wonder if they are crazy. Data from this study are useful for formators and spiritual directors as well. This data can help them to better understand, and consequently be more helpful to their formees and directees who have been sexually abused.

A previous article (Parappully, 2003) in this Journal based on the same study showed that there is a high prevalence rate of sexual abuse in general Indian society and among those who have opted for a vocation in the Church. It is important to recognize that these survivors need help to put their lives together. They need healing and help to cope with the adverse effects of their traumatic experience. A forthcoming article in this *Journal* will describe what can be done to help survivors of sexual abuse.

Notes

1. Dr. Jose Parappully is a clinical psychologist and Founder-Director of Bosco Psychological Services in New Delhi and Founder-Secretary of Salesian Psychological Association. His research areas include transformation of emotional trauma, and integration of psychology, sexuality and spirituality. He is grateful to Dr. Peter Lourdes and Dr. Joe Mannath who made valuable suggestions on an earlier draft of this article. He can be reached at boscopsych@vsnl.net.

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